

Research paper

Microstructure and ecotoxicological response of Portland cement composites incorporating coal fly ash

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ABSTRACT

Utilization of coal fly ash (FA) as a Portland cement (PC) admixture offers a promising yet underexplored approach to reduce PC's environmental impact and enable sustainable reuse of industrial by-products. This study addresses the gap concerning the technical performance and environmental safety of FA-containing binders (PC-FA). FA characterization via XRD, XRF, EDS, and SEM revealed dominant crystalline phases (quartz, mullite, magnetite, rutile) and a heterogeneous microstructure. Incorporating 10 wt.% and 20 wt.% FA into PC produced denser matrices, refined microstructures, and enhanced pozzolanic activity without compromising mortar integrity (compactness, absence of microcracks, voids and segregation). Bioassays at environmentally relevant concentrations (1 g/L, 0.1 g/L, 0.01 g/L) were carried out on prokaryotic (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and eukaryotic (*Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Artemia salina*, *Sinapis alba*) models. No significant inhibition of bacterial growth was observed. Biofilm formation on all PC surfaces was significantly lower than on polystyrene (reference), with strain-specific effects: FA increased *S. aureus* biofilm formation, while *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* formed less biofilm on FA-doped samples than on PC-REF by up to 2 log₁₀(CFU/cm²). FTIR of PC composites incubated with *E. coli* indicated reduced portlandite and calcite contents, suggesting a lower internal pH and possible chemical disruption under bacteria-favouring conditions. Low toxicity (<10 %) of FA or PC-FA toward *D. subspicatus* and *A. salina* was determined. Low phytotoxicity (~70 % germination index) was observed in *S. alba* at high exposure (1 g/L) for all PC types, without FA-related effect. These results support PC-FAs' potential in sustainable construction applications.

1. Introduction

The grow of cement industry is expected to rise by approx. 5.3 % annually up to 2030 [1]. The utilization of coal fly ash (FA) as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) offers promising potential for reducing the environmental burden of Portland cement (PC) production while providing a sustainable solution for the management of industrial by-products [2,3]. FA, particularly from lignite combustion, contains pozzolanic components such as aluminosilicates and iron oxides that enhance the performance of blended binders and support the development of low-carbon construction materials [4,5]. Despite increasing

environmental regulations, lignite remains a significant energy source in several countries, notably in the Czech Republic, where it accounted for 33.5 % of electricity generation in 2024, the highest share in the EU [6]. As a result, large volumes of FA are still produced annually, presenting both an opportunity for resource recovery and a challenge for safe disposal [7].

While FA is widely recognized for its beneficial use in concrete, cement, and mortar [8], less than 30 % of the global production is currently utilized; the remainder is stored in landfills, ponds, or through surface stacking, which may lead to long-term environmental risks [9]. A key limitation to broader FA reuse is the variability in its

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mineralogical and chemical composition, governed by coal type, combustion technology, and emission control systems [10,11]. Use of high-quality coal can effectively reduce the emission of particulate matters which cause various adverse effect on human body [12,13]. Additionally, FA often contains so-called “hazardous heavy metals (HMs)” such as As, Cd, Cr, Hg, Ni, Pb, and Zn, whose release into the environment can pose serious ecotoxicological risks [14,15]. Both laboratory and field studies have analogically revealed that leaching of HMs from FA is strongly dependent on pH, coal combustion temperature, and varying natural environmental conditions, such as surface and ground water redox potential [16]. Based on that, HMs leaching can negatively affect the health, growth, and reproduction of various organisms, including potential bioaccumulation and cytotoxic effects [17].

To mitigate these risks, FA has been studied not only as a construction additive but also as a binder component in stabilization/solidification (S/S) systems for HM immobilization [18,19]. PC-based binders are frequently employed for this purpose due to their wide availability, mechanical strength, and favourable performance in engineering applications. Immobilization mechanisms include both chemical stabilization - incorporation of metal ions into PC/FA hydration products, and physical encapsulation [20]. Cement materials can also reduce surface area available for leaching of HMs [21,22]. Currently, researchers focus mainly on solidification/stabilization technology, with littler attention paid to the environmental risk after stabilization [23,24].

Likewise, the environmental cost of PC production cannot be overlooked. With approximately 0.81 kg of CO₂ emitted per kg of PC produced, the cement industry is responsible for an estimated 8 % of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [25,26]. Partial replacement of PC with FA can thus markedly reduce the carbon footprint of construction materials while enabling long-term immobilization of HMs. Valorising FA in this way conserves resources, minimizes waste, advances cement industry decarbonization and minimizes environmental impact of PC-based materials [27–29].

Despite intensive and broad research on the mechanical and durability performance of FA–PC composites, studies specifically addressing the impact of FA substitution on HM immobilization, especially under conditions simulating real-world exposure, e.g., high humidity curing, remain scarce and limited. Therefore, further investigations are required to evaluate both the environmental safety and technical performance of low-carbon, FA-containing binders, particularly in the context of HM-contaminated waste streams.

Prior to the application of novel cementitious materials, not only the technical performance of FA binders, but also their impact on biological systems should be thoroughly studied, as their ecotoxicological impact has been researched insufficiently so far [30]. PC is broadly recognized for its intrinsic toxicity toward microorganisms and other organisms, primarily due to its highly alkaline pore solution (pH often ≥ 12), which compromises cell membranes, disrupts enzyme activity, and impairs metabolism, ultimately inhibiting bacterial and eukaryotic viability and growth [30]. This potent toxic effect is most prominent in freshly hydrated cement, whereas ageing via carbonation and hydraulic reactions reduces free Ca(OH)₂ content and lowers surface pH, diminishing its toxic potential towards biological systems over time [31]. Moreover, carbonation is recognized as an effective technique for stabilizing HMs through coprecipitation, as the metal ions are immobilized by trapping within the structure of a newly formed calcium carbonate precipitate [32,33].

When PC is modified with admixtures such as nanoparticles (e.g., ZnO, TiO₂), FA, or other industrial by-products, the ecotoxicological profile may change significantly. ZnO combined with nanosilica, for example, has been shown to suppress the growth of *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*, improving PC hydration and mechanical properties [34,35]. TiO₂ contributed to PC antimicrobial activity, achieving a 100 % bacterial killing rate [36]. In contrast, FA amendments often moderate initial alkalinity—potentially reducing acute bacterial toxicity—but risk leaching heavy metals depending on ash composition and

environmental conditions [30,37]. Regarding the impact of PC on eukaryotic organisms, the conclusions of published studies vary and, as in the case of microorganisms, point to substantial variation in interactions between specific materials and organisms. A range of effects on plant development was observed following exposure to PC, as assessed using standardized plant-based ecotoxicological bioassays. A direct toxic effect in terms of germination to groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) was observed after exposure to a high dose of PC (25 g/kg of soil) which can be found in PC dust-polluted soil [38]. For *Allium cepa* and *Lepidium sativum*, no effect was observed in terms of the germination index; however, a DNA damage was increased on the emerged seedlings after exposure to concrete leachates [39]. Exposing lichens to an excess of calcium decreased the content of *chlorophyll a* and soluble proteins and changed other physiological characteristics [40]. Higher eukaryotes like fish are similarly unable to tolerate PC contamination. Acute toxicity studies on rainbow trout revealed histological changes in the gills, necroses in liver tissue, and fat granules after exposure to 0.5 g/L of cement [41]. Furthermore, an increase in water parameters (pH, turbidity, and conductivity) were noted [42]. Contrary to the findings observed in fish, crustaceans appear to be more resilient. For the PC leachates, low acute toxicity to *Daphnia magna* was found, but this was only with extended contact time [43]. With chronic exposure, the increased toxicity may be observed not only in terms of mortality, but also in parameters such as body length [44].

Collectively, the above findings indicate that the toxicity of cementitious materials towards bacteria and higher organisms is a complex, time-dependent phenomenon. The identity, concentration, and chemical form of the additive play a decisive role in determining the ecological biostability of the final material. Therefore, risk assessment requires standardized leaching protocols and multi-endpoint biological testing.

As the biological responses of specific species to FA-doped PC remain largely unexplored, the primary objective of this study is to address this research gap by preparing novel PC composites reinforced with FA and systematically evaluate their performance through a multi-level approach. To our knowledge, we present highly novel, comprehensive, multidisciplinary investigation offering critical insights into the ecotoxicological behaviour of PC blends containing energy-sector by-products. For the broader application of such PC blends, ecotoxicological assessment is as essential as evaluating their structural, mechanical, and durability properties, which are comparatively well understood. The conducted research addresses the deficiency in the existing literature by incorporating ecotoxicological evaluations into the development and application of sustainable blended binders. Specifically, we (i) characterize the chemical composition and microstructural evolution of the composites, (ii) assess their influence on bacterial growth, biofilm formation, and interactions with the composite matrix, and (iii) evaluate ecotoxicological effects on representative eukaryotic organisms including the freshwater algae *D. subspicatus*, the aquatic crustacean *Artemia salina*, and the higher plant *Sinapis alba*. A significant contribution of this study also lies in the broad range of parameters investigated: we evaluate different FA contents in the PC matrix, environmentally relevant concentration ranges of FA and PC materials in interactions with microorganisms, and species-specific responses to these materials. By integrating material characterization with multi-endpoint biological testing, this study provides a holistic assessment of technical performance and environmental safety and delivers a transferable methodological platform for future research. It is important to note, however, that the scope of the study is restricted to toxicity data pertaining to the specific prokaryotic and eukaryotic model organisms examined.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw materials

The investigated mortars were prepared from ordinary PC – CEM I

42.5R (Českomoravský cement, a.s., Radotín, Czech Republic), FA (Vřesová, Czech Republic), quartz sand, and tap water. The used FA was a by-product from lignite and natural gas combustion and was collected on a three-step electrostatic precipitator with selected separation efficiency. Details on the cycle power plant (organization of 5 boilers, waste processing, and lignite parameters can be found in our previous study [20]). As aggregates, three fractions of sorted silica were mixed, having particle sizes of 0–0.5 mm, 0.5–1.0 mm, and 1.0–2.0 mm, respectively. The sand was delivered by Filtrační písky, a.s., Chlum u Doky, Czech Republic.

2.2. PC samples preparation and characterization

In the composition of mortars, PC (chemical composition specified in **Table S1**) was partially substituted by FA. The substitution ratio was 10 and 20 wt.% (samples labelled PC-FA10, PC-FA20, respectively). The selected replacement levels were based on the findings of our previous study [20], in which a similar type of FA was investigated as a supplementary cementitious material at 5, 10, 15, and 20 % substitution rates by cement mass. The results showed that the strength activity index (SAI) obtained for the 20 % replacement level reached a value of 0.75 (measured for 28-day samples), which represents the threshold generally accepted for classifying a material as pozzolanic according to relevant references [45,46] and standard ASTM C618 [47]. Therefore, in the present work, the 20 % replacement was chosen as the upper limit for PC substitution, while the 10 % level was included to represent a moderate degree of replacement that still ensures sufficient mechanical performance. These two substitution ratios were considered optimal for the subsequent ecotoxicity assessment, as they reflect both a realistic range of FA utilization in cement-based materials and the boundary beyond which the mechanical and durability properties could be negatively affected. By selecting these two representative FA dosages, the influence of increasing FA content on the potential release of hazardous substances and the overall environmental compatibility of the mortars was effectively evaluated.

The control sample, made of silica aggregate and PC as the only binder, was designated PC-REF. The water/binder mass ratio was 0.5 and was kept constant for all prepared mortars. The water/binder ratio was chosen to get for the control, reference mortars, values of spread 160×160 mm, which was verified in flow table test conducted in accordance with EN 12350-5 [48]. The binder/aggregate mass ratio was 1/3, which is typical for testing PC strength. The proportioning of samples is together with flow table test results summarized in **Table 1**. Due to the complex morphology of FA, the workability of the fresh mortars was slightly reduced; however, it remained adequate for proper sample casting. The samples were mixed in compliance with EN 196-1 [49]. The FA and PC were initially blended in a planetary mixer for 30 s to ensure a uniform distribution of the binder components. Subsequently, the predetermined amount of water was added, and the mixing process continued for another 30 s. Afterwards, the standard sand was gradually introduced, and the mixture was further blended for 60 s. To achieve complete homogenization, the material adhering to the walls and bottom of the mixing bowl was manually scraped off during a 90 s period of hand mixing. Finally, the mortar was remixed mechanically for an additional 60 s to obtain a consistent mixture.

The fresh mixtures were placed into plastic moulds (40/40/160 mm) and covered with plastic foil to prevent excessive drying. The samples

Table 1
Composition of prepared mortars (kg/m^3) and spread diameter of fresh mixtures (mm).

Mortar	CEM I	FA	Sand	Water	Spread diameter
PC-REF	522.6	-	1567.7	261.3	160/160
PC-FA10	444.2	78.4	1567.7	261.3	150/150
PC-FA20	418.1	104.5	1567.7	261.3	155/150

were demoulded after approx. one day and cured in an air-conditioned laboratory ($T = 23 \pm 2$ °C and $RH = 90 \pm 5$ %) until testing. The entire PC samples preparation process is shown in **Fig. 1**.

Phase composition of both the FA and PC samples was evaluated by X-ray diffraction (XRD). Diffractograms were recorded using a Bruker D2 Phaser powder diffractometer equipped with a Cu X-ray tube. The Axios sequential wave-dispersive X-ray spectrometer was used to carry out X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF). All spectral line intensities of the elements were measured in a vacuum using the SuperQ 5.0 program. The obtained intensities were processed using the Omnia program without the need to measure standards. The microstructure and morphology of the fracture surfaces were analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and optical microscopy (OM). SEM analysis was performed using a Tescan Lyra microscope equipped with a field emission gun (FEG) electron source. Data evaluation was performed using AZtecEnergy software. OM was carried out using a Navitar macro-optics system, and images were captured with a Sony 2/3" digital camera (5 MP resolution). Image acquisition and processing were carried out using NIS-Elements BR 5.21.02 software with the Extended Depth of Focus (EDF) module. In addition, elemental maps were obtained using energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) using the XMax150 analyzer.

2.3. Bacterial strains, eukaryotic organisms, and culture conditions

Three standard reference bacterial strains, commonly employed for antibacterial disc susceptibility testing, were selected as model microorganisms. These were obtained from the Czech Collection of Microorganisms (CCM, Czech Republic) and included the Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 (CCM 3953 equivalent) and two Gram-negative species: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 (CCM 3954 equivalent) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 (CCM 3955 equivalent). For the ecotoxicological assessments described below, pure cultures were prepared by static incubation in sterile tryptic soy broth (TSB) at 37 °C for 24 h. In addition to bacterial models, the testing set comprised three eukaryotic species: the aquatic crustacean *Artemia salina* (Easyfish, Czech Republic), the plant *Sinapis alba* (mustard; Biom, Czech Republic), and the freshwater green algae *Desmodesmus subspicatus* (Institute of Botany, Třeboň, Czech Republic).

2.4. Biological assay

2.4.1. PC toxicity to bacteria

The effect of FA (at concentrations of 1, 0.1, and 0.01 g/L) and PC (1 g/L) materials on **bacterial growth** was evaluated as described in our previous study [50]. Bacterial cultures with the tested materials (powdered form) were incubated under continuous mixing at 37 °C, and optical density at 600 nm was monitored for 18 h (BioTek Synergy H1 Multimode Reader; Agilent, USA). Growth curves were generated from blank-corrected values, and the maximum specific growth rate was calculated from the exponential phase by linear regression.

The effect of the PC materials on **bacterial biofilm formation** was assessed following the approach described in our previous study [51]. Sterile (UV 30 min) material pieces ($1 \times 1 \times 1$ cm) were statically incubated with *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, or *P. aeruginosa* suspensions (0.5 McF) at 37 °C for 48 h. Biofilm cells released from the material surface by sonication were serially diluted, plated on tryptone soy agar (TSA), and incubated for CFU determination (normalized to 1 cm^2). Polystyrene (bottom of the 12-well plate) served as a reference material. In addition, SEM and EDS analyses were performed as described above to visualize surface-adhered bacteria and confirm the presence of organic matter.

2.4.2. FTIR analysis of microbial effect on PC chemical structure

Microbial influence on the chemical structure of PC-REF, PC-FA10 and PC-FA20 composite matrix was evaluated using FTIR. First, sterile material pieces ($1 \times 1 \times 1$ cm) were statically incubated with *E. coli* suspension (0.5 McF) at 37 °C for 48 h; one set of the PC materials was

Fig. 1. A schematic of the sample preparation process.

left as a reference (cultivated in sterile TSB medium, unexposed to *E. coli*). After the cultivation, PCs were rinsed in sterile distilled water, dried in an oven and ground in a MM 400 (Retsch) ball mill. Subsequently, they were homogenised in an agate grinding mortar and analysed directly using the ATR technique on a diamond crystal. The infrared spectra were collected after 32 scans at 4 cm^{-1} resolution in absorbance mode using FTIR Nicolet 6700 spectrometer (Thermo Scientific). The corrected spectra were deconvoluted to confirm the main compound groups.

2.4.3. PC toxicity to eukaryotic organisms

The test samples were prepared in the same way for all tests performed with eukaryotes. The material was dispersed as a powder in a control medium specific to each organism, and then sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for 30 min. Solutions of different concentrations were then prepared and used immediately for tests with different organisms. The concentrations tested ranged from 0.01 to 1 g/L for *Artemia salina* and *Sinapis alba*, while for *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, only concentrations from 0.01 to 0.1 g/L were used due to possible shielding effects on the results.

The **algal growth inhibition test on *D. subspicatus*** was conducted according to standard EN ISO 8692 using the same procedures as reported in our previous study [51]. Algae were exposed to different samples for 72 h under continuous light. Growth rate inhibition was assessed based on measurements under a light microscope at 400x magnification (Primo Star, Zeiss, Germany). Bold's Basal medium was used as a control in the algae test. Prior experiment, the algae culture was in the exponential phase. The test was considered valid if there was no increase in the control's pH of more than 1.5 by the end.

The ***A. salina* acute toxicity** assay followed the same methodology as in our earlier work [51], including hatching conditions, exposure concentrations, and mortality assessment after 24 h, as well as possible bioaccumulation visible under the light microscope. In the *A. salina* test, a sodium chloride solution was used as the negative control, while a potassium dichromate solution was used as the positive control. A test was considered valid if the mortality rate in the control group was 10 % or less.

The **phytotoxicity test using mustard *S. alba* seeds** was carried out as previously described [50], using 15 seeds per Petri dish, exposed to test solutions for 72 h in the dark. After the incubation period, the number of germinated seeds was determined, and root length was measured using ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health, USA). The results obtained were then expressed as the germination index (GI), indicating phytotoxicity according to Eq.:

$$GI = \frac{N_S \times L_S}{N_C \times L_C} \times 100 [\%]$$

where N_S is the number of germinated seeds in the sample; N_C is the number of germinated seeds in control; L_S is the average root length in the sample; L_C is the average root length in control. A value below 50 % indicates high phytotoxicity; 50–80 % indicates modest phytotoxicity; 80–100 % indicates no phytotoxicity. When the GI value is higher than 100 %, it is considered that the sample tested is a phytonutrient or a phytostimulant [52]. In the mustard seed test, the medium used to prepare the material dispersions served as the negative control. A potassium dichromate solution was used as the positive control. The test was considered valid if, after 72 h, more than 90 % of the seeds had germinated in the negative control and germination had been inhibited in the positive control.

2.5. Data analysis

All biological experiments were performed in at least three biological and three technical replicates to ensure data reliability, following the validated protocols from previous studies [50,51]. Statistical analysis was conducted as described in our previous work using the R programming language [51]. Briefly, outliers were identified and removed, data normality was assessed, and one-way ANOVA followed by appropriate post hoc tests (Tukey HSD and Bonferroni correction) was applied. Significance level was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. The analysis aimed to verify whether the tested materials affected model organisms' growth and viability.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Raw materials characterization

The phase composition of the FA was determined by XRD (see Fig. 2). Results showed the presence of crystalline phases including quartz, mullite, magnetite and rutile. These phases are consistent with those commonly reported in coal and coal ash samples worldwide, where quartz, clay-derived phases, sulfides, and others are frequently observed [53]. The XRD analysis of PC facilitated the identification of its primary crystalline phases (Figure S1), specifically alite, belite, tricalcium aluminate, brownmillerite, and gypsum, which are characteristic components of CEM I type cement. The chemical composition of the FA was evaluated by XRF. As expected, the sample was primarily composed of carbon, oxygen and other light elements, silicon, and aluminum. The

Fig. 2. Diffractogram of FA obtained by XRD.

content of the elements in the sample is shown in Table 2. Results from XRF correspond with elemental maps obtained by EDS. Main oxides forming PC used are shown in Supporting Information (Figure S2).

Elemental mapping performed on the FA sample using EDS revealed the heterogeneous distribution of several major and minor elements (see Fig. 3). Silicon and aluminium are among the dominant elements, suggesting the presence of aluminosilicate phases, most likely quartz and mullite, which is in good agreement with the XRD results. Iron is distributed in localized areas, likely indicating the presence of magnetite or other iron oxides. Titanium appears in discrete spots, consistent with the presence of rutile, a stable high-temperature phase. Calcium and magnesium are present in minor amounts, possibly associated with residual carbonate phases or glassy silicates. Carbon is concentrated in specific regions, indicating the presence of unburnt char or carbon-rich particles. Oxygen is broadly distributed throughout the matrix, as expected for oxidized mineral phases. Overall, the EDS elemental maps support the presence of quartz, mullite, magnetite, and rutile as the main crystalline phases in the sample, in agreement with the XRD analysis.

The image obtained by OM (Fig. 4A) shows accumulated ash particles observed under an optical microscope. The surface exhibits a heterogeneous, porous structure with irregularly shaped agglomerates and interparticle cracks. The microstructure of the FA sample was investigated using SEM. The SEM micrographs in Fig. 4B reveal a typical morphology of FA particles. The sample consists predominantly of spherical particles of various sizes. The size varies from tens of nanometres to tens of micrometres.

3.2. Composites characterization

The properties and structure of composite mortars, especially those prepared with blended binders, evolve over time depending on the curing conditions. In our study, all tests were performed on samples

Table 2

The composition of FA obtained by XRF (other oxides = oxides with <0.10 wt.% concentration).

Oxides	wt.%	Oxides	wt.%
C + other light elements	6.50	CaO	2.62
Na ₂ O	0.45	TiO ₂	6.83
MgO	1.37	V ₂ O ₅	0.10
Al ₂ O ₃	26.99	MnO	0.14
SiO ₂	40.68	Fe ₂ O ₃	11.62
P ₂ O ₅	0.43	SrO	0.10
SO ₃	0.56	BaO	0.17
K ₂ O	0.96	Other oxides	0.48

cured for 360 days, at which age we expect only minimal changes in the material parameters with time. The specimens were cured in a climate chamber under controlled conditions of $T = 23 \pm 2$ °C and $RH = 90 \pm 5$ %. The fracture surfaces of the prepared samples were characterized using OM (see Fig. 5). The matrix of the composites exhibits a grey color typical of PC and heterogeneous structure of the prepared composites. Additionally, all micrographs reveal white, brown and grey lustrous particles of silica sand as well as air bubbles in the matrix. With increasing FA content (from PC-FA10 to PC-FA20), the number and size of dark inclusions increase, consistent with the replacement level. No significant signs of poor bonding or interfacial defects between the FA particles and the surrounding matrix were observed, suggesting good compatibility and reactivity of the FA in the cementitious environment.

XRD analysis (Fig. 6) was conducted to identify the crystalline phases in the hardened mortars and to shed light on the hydration process and matrix composition. As expected, we observed quartz from the silica sand, portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), and tricalcium silicate (C_3S) as the main crystalline phases in all samples. The presence of portlandite indicates ongoing hydration of PC [54]. The gradual decrease in its peak intensity in the FA-containing samples suggests its consumption during the pozzolanic reaction, where SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 from the ash react with Ca^{2+} ions to form additional C-S-H and C-A-H gels. This reaction helps densify the matrix and improve durability. The minor amounts of ettringite found in the XRD patterns further confirm the formation of secondary hydration products that can bind heavy metals. Thus, XRD not only verifies the expected phase composition but also provides important information about the reactivity of FA and the chemical processes involved in microstructural development and immobilization performance.

The partial consumption of portlandite during the pozzolanic reaction slightly lowers the alkalinity of the pore solution compared to the reference mortar. This reduction can help from an ecotoxicological perspective, as very high pH values can stress or harm biological systems. A moderate drop in alkalinity can improve biocompatibility while keeping the environment sufficiently alkaline to stabilize hydration products and hold heavy metals in place. Our results (specified below) indicate that the composites with FA did not exhibit increased toxicity. This suggests that the lower pH does not threaten environmental safety and may even improve it by reducing high-pH-related impacts on eukaryotic organisms.

Chemical composition of the prepared sample was determined by XRF, the results are presented in the graphs in Figure S2. All samples primarily contain light elements such as oxygen and hydrogen, originating from clinker minerals and their hydrates, as well as carbon, which may be derived from FA. In addition, elements such as silicon, calcium,

Fig. 3. Elemental maps of FA sample obtained by EDS.

Fig. 4. The structure of FA sample obtained by OM (A); the microstructure of FA obtained by SEM (B).

Fig. 5. Fracture surface of prepared sample set obtained by OM.

aluminum, and iron are present, as they are constituents of clinker phases — tricalcium silicate ($\text{SiO}_2\cdot 3\text{CaO}$), dicalcium silicate ($\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{CaO}$), tricalcium aluminate ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 3\text{CaO}$), and tetracalcium aluminoferrite ($4\text{CaO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$). Sulfur is present due to the addition of gypsum, which is incorporated into PC to regulate the setting process.

The results from SEM show heterogeneous structure of the samples. Typical structure of hydration products of PC is shown on the

micrographs in Fig. 7. PC-REF exhibits a relatively homogeneous structure with well-developed crystalline products, such as needle-like ettringite and plate-like portlandite. In PC-FA10, the matrix becomes denser and smoother, with partially embedded crystalline structures and a more cohesive morphology, suggesting the onset of pozzolanic reactions. In PC-FA20, the microstructure appears more compact and homogeneous, with a further reduction in crystalline features and

Fig. 6. XRD diffraction patterns of PC-REF, PC-FA10, and PC-FA20.

dominance of C–S–H gel, indicating enhanced pozzolanic activity and improved matrix densification. Overall, the increasing FA content leads to a more refined microstructure with reduced visible portlandite and ettringite phases.

The changes observed in the microstructure with increased FA content are closely tied to how the material behaves with respect to durability and leaching. The SEM images in Fig. 7 show that the matrix becomes denser and more uniform, with fewer crystalline portlandite plates and more C–S–H gel. This structure tends to slow down the movement of water and ions through the material, which can improve resistance to chemical attack and lower the release of potentially harmful elements. The smaller amount of portlandite seen in the XRD patterns (Fig. 6) also indicates ongoing pozzolanic reactions, making the matrix more stable and reducing the chances of dissolution processes that could release heavy metals. Additionally, the formation of phases like ettringite and aluminosilicates creates sites where heavy metals can be bound or physically trapped. To better understand how these changes affect long-term performance, future work could include a quantitative phase analysis (e.g., Rietveld refinement), since the relative amounts of portlandite, ettringite, and C–S–H are related to both durability and leaching behaviour.

Previous work on the same system included standardized leaching tests after 28 and 90 days of curing [55]. This work confirmed that the concentrations of heavy metals such as As, Ba, Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, and Zn released from the FA and cement mortars remained well below regulatory limits. Even As, Ba and Cu, which concentrations in dry matter of FA exceeded the safe limits for FA disposal in the form of backfilling, were safely immobilized. Similar low leaching concentrations have been reported elsewhere [56–58]. The results also showed that leaching tended to decrease with longer curing time. This indicates that the microstructure matured and pozzolanic reactions continued, leading to progressive immobilization. This behaviour stems from both the chemical binding of heavy metals into hydration products, such as C–S–H,

ettringite, or aluminosilicate phases, and physical encapsulation within a dense matrix with low permeability. Even metals that were in excess in the original FA, such as As, Cu, and Ba, were successfully stabilized in the cement structure. Although the leaching results under standard conditions show good environmental stability, the long-term behaviour of the composites may change if the surrounding pH decreases. Many heavy metals become more soluble in acidic conditions [59,60], such as those caused by carbonation or acid rain. This change could lead to increased release over time. The creation of stable phases like C–S–H, ettringite, or metal silicates, along with the dense microstructure of the matrix, can help limit this effect. However, future work should involve tests under different pH conditions to better predict long-term environmental performance.

3.3. Impact of FA and PC materials on bacteria

The prepared and characterized materials were evaluated for their biological effects on both prokaryotic and eukaryotic systems. The tested concentrations of FA and PC (1 g/L, 0.1 g/L and 0.01 g/L) representing various environmental exposure scenarios were selected to align with published studies, enabling comparison and eliciting observable biological responses [50,51]. Model organisms included in this study were selected as representative species commonly used in ecotoxicological studies, enabling meaningful comparison with existing literature and reflecting their relevance to both material degradation and human health [51]. The prokaryotic species *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa* serve as indicators of microbial toxicity and surface interactions relevant to environmental and human health contexts. The eukaryotic models *D. subspicatus*, *A. salina*, and *S. alba* reflect primary producers and consumers across aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, and are typically used to determine ecotoxicological properties in both the relevant literature and legislation. *A. salina* is commonly used in experiments to represent saltwater organisms due to its ability to survive in environments with low and very high salinity. Conversely, the genus *Artemia* is representative of zooplankton and is considered highly sensitive to environmental contaminants [61]. *S. alba* is a representative of terrestrial organisms. As a primary producer, it is widely used in tests to determine the impact of soil contamination. In some studies, its seeds are also used to evaluate the effects on agricultural land [62]. *D. subspicatus*, a unicellular green algae, is a freshwater bioindicator that plays a crucial role in understanding the impact on primary producers. Also, this species is recommended by guidelines for growth inhibition tests [63]. Together, these organisms enable a holistic evaluation of the FA- and PC-composites' ecotoxicological profile and their potential environmental implications.

First, the impact of materials on model bacterial growth (growth kinetics and maximum growth rate) and biofilm formation on material surfaces was assessed. Bacteria were selected based on their differences in cell wall composition (Gram-positive *S. aureus* vs. Gram-negative *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*) and cell morphology (cocci *S. aureus* vs. rod *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*) and size. Monitoring bacterial growth over 18 h in the presence of the materials revealed no significant changes in growth dynamics (Fig. 8). Minor absorbance shifts observed in the presence of FA and PC materials were attributed to their inherent optical (light-absorbing) properties rather than alterations in microbial proliferation. Based on that, no species-specific differences were observed; thus, the above-mentioned bacterial characteristics did not play a role in this interaction. A significant change in maximum growth rate (Fig. 8) was observed in only one of the three bacteria tested, *E. coli*, with a positive impact of materials on maximal growth speed. These results contrast with findings for other materials, such as nanotube- and graphene-reinforced magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) composites, where *P. aeruginosa* consistently exhibited higher resistance to materials than *S. aureus* and *E. coli* [50,51]. Although *P. aeruginosa* is typically the most resistant of the three, no significant differences were observed among the bacteria in the FA and PC samples tested. Generally,

Fig. 7. SEM micrographs of PC-REF, PC-FA10, and PC-FA20 in three magnifications.

a material-dependent trend was observed. The addition of FA slightly increased growth rate, both with and without PC, likely due to trace elements in the ash. Ions such as Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Cu^{2+} are essential at low concentrations, serving as cofactors or prosthetic groups for enzymes and proteins.

Next, we studied biofilm formation on the PC samples surface. Biofilms represent a natural microbial state that enhances resistance to external stressors. However, on building materials, they can accelerate degradation and reduce material quality. Regarding biofilm formation on PC materials surface (Fig. 9), all tested bacteria formed less biofilm on PC surfaces compared to the control (polystyrene). This is likely due to the inherently high alkalinity of cement, as the tested bacteria prefer neutral pH conditions [64]; exposure to elevated pH reduces their surface proliferation on PC. However, material- and strain-specific

behaviour was observed. Generally, *P. aeruginosa* exhibited greater biofilm formation than *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, consistent with its higher invasiveness. The incorporation of FA into PC reduced *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* biofilm formation for up to $2 \log_{10}(\text{CFU}/\text{cm}^2)$ compared to PC-REF, while *S. aureus* showed higher biofilm formation on PC-FA10 and PC-FA20 than on PC-REF surface. These quantitative results are supported by SEM and EDS analyses (Fig. 10), confirming that all three tested bacteria attached to and colonized the PC surface, regardless of its functionalization with FA. The observed strain-specific responses in biofilm formation likely reflect distinct physiological and surface-adherence traits of each bacterium, influencing their interaction with the cement composite matrix. *P. aeruginosa* typically exhibits robust biofilm-forming capacity due to its efficient quorum sensing and exopolysaccharide production (alginate, Pel, Psl), which enhance

Fig. 8. A) Bacterial growth in the presence of FA (1 g/L, 0.1 g/L, 0.01 g/L), PC-REF (1 g/L), PC-FA10 (1 g/L) and PC-FA20 (1 g/L), respectively: a) *S. aureus*, b) *E. coli*, c) *P. aeruginosa*; B) maximum growth rate of bacteria in the presence of FA (1 g/L, 0.1 g/L, 0.01 g/L), PC-REF (1 g/L), PC-FA10 (1 g/L) and PC-FA20 (1 g/L), respectively (means that do not share a letter within the same column are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$).

surface adhesion even under adverse conditions [65,66]. In contrast, *E. coli* biofilm formation is more sensitive to environmental stress, particularly high pH and ionic strength, which can disrupt cell surface charge and reduce attachment efficiency [67]. *S. aureus* tolerates alkaline conditions to some extent, and its biofilm formation on FA-doped cement may be promoted by surface roughness or localized charge

heterogeneity introduced by FA particles. The enhanced *S. aureus* adhesion could also relate to its ability to express surface adhesins that recognize mineral and oxide surfaces [68].

Our results correspond to the conclusions of published studies. FA in its raw state typically shows minimal antibacterial activity; however, purification or enhancement with various substances, such as

Fig. 9. Biofilm formation of *S. aureus* (SA), *E. coli* (EC) and *P. aeruginosa* (PA) on the surface of PC materials; quantitative analysis (means that do not share a letter within the same column are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$).

nanoparticles, improves its efficacy. For example, a purified FA reduced the growth of *E. coli* by approximately 8.7 % and *Bacillus cereus* by nearly 59.9 % relative to control cultures [69]. FA-based geopolymer mortars cured at ~ 100 °C exhibited strong antimicrobial activity tested via a standard disk diffusion method, forming inhibition zones of up to ~ 49 mm, likely due to their high alkalinity and refined microstructure [70]. Enhanced composites combining FA, metakaolin, and 2.5 wt% nano-TiO₂ showed superior antibacterial efficacy against *E. coli*, *Candida albicans*, and *P. aeruginosa* compared to the unmodified formulation [71]. FA-derived ceramics loaded with silver nanoparticles demonstrated potent and prolonged bactericidal action against both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, governed by nanoparticle size and release profiles [72]. Similarly, PC effect is highly dependent on several factors, especially bacterial strain, cement composition, and environmental conditions, which makes it difficult to draw general conclusions. In previously published studies, PC typically inhibited the model bacterial strains used in this work. A recent study reported that PC-based surfaces significantly reduced *E. coli* viability by up to 1.1 log₁₀ within 4 h incubation on PC surface [73]. Modified cementitious composites, especially those reinforced or doped (e.g., with ZnO or SiO₂), have demonstrated inhibitory effects on *S. aureus*, as evidenced by reduced biofilm formation and optical density *in vitro* [35]. While data on *P. aeruginosa* are more limited in the context of plain PC, antimicrobial cement composites have inhibited marine bacteria such as *Serratia marcescens*, suggesting broader microbial suppression in specialized cement formulations [74].

3.4. Bacterial effect on PC composite chemical structure

Further, we analysed the microbial impact on the chemical composition of the composite matrix. Based on the above-described results, *E. coli* was selected as a model organism. This analysis builds on the general understanding that interactions between composite matrices and prokaryotes involve two key aspects: potential ecotoxicological risks and the deterioration of building materials, i.e., the chemical effects of microorganisms on the composite structure. A comparison can be made between the pure matrix and the matrix that has been attacked by microorganisms using NIR spectrometry analysis. Biogenic organic acids (such as acetic, lactic, butyric and the like) and carbon dioxide, which are released by microorganisms, can be extremely corrosive to concrete [75]. Microbial growth can further reduce the surface pH of concrete, leading to significant biogenic production of polythionic and sulfuric acid. This theory was verified on PC-REF, PC-FA10 and PC-FA20

samples (Fig. 11).

Some regions of the NIR spectra of cement composites show characteristic absorption bands. A typical example is the O – H stretching vibration in water, which is a broad band with a peak at 3407 cm⁻¹. Other important bands are those originating from the O – H bond in portlandite at 3645 cm⁻¹. Another band confirms the presence of calcite around 1400 and at 873 cm⁻¹. The characteristic major absorption band at 1086 cm⁻¹ due to the S – O stretching vibration in ettringite can be also detected. The presence of FA in PC composites results in a decrease in portlandite (at 3645 cm⁻¹), which is consumed in the pozzolanic reaction. It also slows down the carbonation reaction, as observed by the decrease in band intensity at 873 cm⁻¹. The peak area ratios of O – H bond and carbonation shows Table 3.

The symmetric and antisymmetric vibrations of the Si – O and Al – O bonds in the hydrated amorphous phases of silicate and aluminate occur at ~ 1000 cm⁻¹ as an intensive absorption band. A doublet at ~ 800 cm⁻¹, assigned to the polymeric unit of SiO₄⁴⁻, AlO₄⁵⁻, increases in intensity with an increasing C/S ratio [76]. The absorption band at 700–400 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the rocking motion of the oxygen atoms in the Si – O, Al – O, and Fe – O bonds in the hydrated cement phases.

For bacterial identification, the region between 1600 and 700 cm⁻¹ is important. This region comprises the absorption bands of amide at ~ 1500 cm⁻¹ and the mixed region of proteins, lipids and carbohydrates between 1500 and 1300 cm⁻¹. The nucleic acid region appears at ~ 1230 cm⁻¹, the polysaccharide region between 1200 and 900 cm⁻¹, and finally the fingerprint region is present below 900 cm⁻¹ [77]. The absorption bands of organic and inorganic compounds overlap each other in the obtained spectra.

However, when comparing the reference sample and the samples exposed to *E. coli*, it is clear that has been a reduction in the concentration of portlandite and calcite, which will lead to a lowering of the pH inside the material and later, in case of the presence of sufficient concentration *E. coli* bacteria and proper conditions for their viability, disruption of the chemical equilibrium of the resulting hydration products. However, further studies are necessary to observe long-time effect of bacteria growth on FA modified PC composites.

3.5. Impact of FA and PC materials on eukaryotes

Results for *D. subspicatus* growth inhibition showed no statistically significant effect ($p > 0.05$) under the tested concentrations for reference and PC-FA composites (see Table 4). The low observed toxicity (below 10 %) of PC-REF or composites is consistent with the findings of previous MOC composites testing [51]. Although the aqueous suspension of PC-REF is highly alkaline, mainly due to the calcium hydroxide, formed during cement hydration, in the presence of atmospheric carbon dioxide, the occurrence of carbonation results in a reduction of the alkalinity. Thus, during a 72 h exposure period, the alkaline pH may decrease towards neutral values to which freshwater algae can adapt. For instance, *Chlorella vulgaris* maintained its morphology, including its colour, chloroplast shape and cellular integrity, over a pH range of 4 to 11.5 [78]. A higher pH value may also be protective by reducing the bioavailability of certain metals. Another study demonstrated aluminium toxicity towards several freshwater organisms at a pH 6 [79].

Saltwater crustaceans *A. salina* were exposed to concentrations of references and PC-FA composites ranged from 0.01 to 1 g/L. Even at the highest tested concentration of 1 g/L, no significant toxicity ($p > 0.05$) towards *A. salina* was observed (see Table 4). The mortality results were below 10 % and no bioaccumulation in crustaceans' bodies was found under a light microscope, which indicates low acute toxicity under the tested conditions. Unlike MOC, which has been reported to induce significant mortality in *A. salina* (from 0.01 g/L), PC-REF did not show comparable toxicity [51]. This effect may be attributed to the lower solubility of PC in aqueous media, limited bioavailability, or chemical

Fig. 10. Biofilm formation of *S. aureus* (SA), *E. coli* (EC) and *P. aeruginosa* (PA) on the surface of PC materials: A) SEM analysis, B) EDS elemental maps of PC materials.

Fig. 11. NIR spectra of PC-REF and samples exposed to action of *E. coli*, namely PC-REF-EC, PC-FA10-EC, and PC-FA20-EC.

Table 3

Peak area ratios of O – H bond and carbonation.

Samples	Peak area ratio at 3645 cm ⁻¹	Peak area ratio at 873 cm ⁻¹
PC-REF-EC	0.0908	0.1240
PC-FA10-EC	0.0569	0.1102
PC-FA20-EC	0.0496	0.0915

Table 4

Results of *Artemia salina* mortality after 24 h exposure and growth inhibition (I) of *Desmodesmus subspicatus* exposed to reference samples and PC-FA composites for 72 h.

Sample	c [g/L]	<i>A. salina</i> Mortality (%)	<i>D. subspicatus</i> I (%)
PC-REF	0.01	6.7 ± 4.7	-3.6 ± 0.8
	0.1	6.7 ± 5.8	3.7 ± 0.6
	1	3.3 ± 5.8	-
FA	0.01	0	2.2 ± 4.0
	0.1	0	3.1 ± 0.4
	1	3.3 ± 4.7	-
PC-FA10	0.01	6.7 ± 4.7	3.5 ± 4.7
	0.1	3.3 ± 5.8	-0.8 ± 2.1
	1	3.3 ± 5.8	-
PC-FA20	0.01	3.3 ± 5.8	1.3 ± 1.4
	0.1	6.7 ± 4.7	0.9 ± 2.6
	1	3.3 ± 4.7	-

composition. *Artemia* sp. also have the ability to adapt to diverse conditions, including changes in the pH values [80].

The results of the germination index (GI) as determined after exposure to *S. alba* seeds are shown in Fig. 12. GI integrates seed germination rate and root elongation measurements, offering a comprehensive evaluation of plant development. The sample with a value greater than 80 % is not considered as phytotoxic, whereas a value below this threshold is associated with a phytotoxic effect. The slight phytotoxic effect on mustard seeds was observed only for the highest tested concentration (1 g/L) of PC-REF and its composites with a germination index around 70 %. The fact that PC-REF had the highest toxicity suggests that the main cause of the observed effects are linked to substances and minerals found in cement itself, rather than to FA or preparation methods. However, a concentration of 1 g/L is only environmentally relevant in the event of industry runoff or an accident. Observed effects may be attributed to parameters such as alkaline conditions or cement “burns” from calcium hydroxide formation, with a known physiological impact on plants [81–83]. Plants are the most sensitive to abiotic stress

Fig. 12. Germination index of *Sinapis alba* seeds after exposure to references and PC-FA composites for 72 h. The dashed line is an indicator of phytotoxicity with a germination index less than 80 %. Means that do not share a letter are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

from environmental pollution at the early stage of seedling, which subsequently affects the entire development process and thus the resulting yield in agriculture.

3.6. Benchmarking against recent literature

To summarise our findings and place them in the context of published studies, Table 5 emphasizes key performance and biosafety metrics for the FA-reinforced PC composites alongside representative state-of-the-art reports. The benchmarking spans microstructure, internal alkalinity, cross-species bioassay outcomes (bacteria, algae, crustaceans, plants) at environmentally relevant exposures (1, 0.1, 0.01 g/L), and overall study scope. Consistencies with prior work are indicated, and advances unique to this study are highlighted. Where differences appear, we note likely mechanisms (e.g., FA content, dose) to aid interpretation. Overall, this synthesis clarifies the novelty of our approach and delineates the conditions under which the present composites couple robust materials performance with low ecotoxicological risk.

4. Limitations and Future research

Despite the comprehensive approach, several limitations warrant mention, particularly regarding long-term applicability and real-world environmental conditions. Regarding the materials, the PC composites microstructure and chemical stability evolve during curing and weathering, thus their performance could be monitored in various stages. The biological tests were conducted under controlled laboratory conditions that may not fully reflect the complexity of natural environments, where variable pH, temperature, salinity, and organic matter can influence material behaviour and microbial responses. The selected model organisms, although standard in ecotoxicological testing, represent only a limited portion of environmental and human-relevant biota, and their sensitivity may differ from that of other taxa. Especially, biofilm experiments were conducted in single-species systems, whereas in real environments, multispecies biofilms and complex microbial communities usually predominate and may display distinct adhesion and degradation dynamics. Also, the short-term exposures used here may underestimate potential chronic or cumulative effects of leachates released over longer timescales.

Table 5

Literature benchmarking of FA-reinforced PC composites across materials and biosafety endpoints, divided into specific dimensions.

Dimension	This study (PC-FA composites)	Representative studies	Benchmark vs. literature	Refs.
Microstructure (pozzolanic reaction)	XRD/FTIR: reduced portlandite and calcite; increased C-S-H; denser matrix (SEM).	FA commonly consumes portlandite and increases C-S-H; densification over curing and with FA activation.	Consistent; our coupling of microstructure with bacterial incubation/FTIR adds mechanistic context.	[84,85]
Internal alkalinity / pH implications	FA lowered internal alkalinity (lower portlandite/calcite), mitigating high-pH stress.	Toxicity of concrete leachates often driven by high pH and conductivity; reducing surface/pore pH can reduce adhesion and toxicity. Excess Ca exposure in lichens reduced chlorophyll a and soluble proteins and altered physiological status.	Aligned; our linked bioassays support this mechanism.	[39,86, 87]
Bacterial growth (planktonic)	No significant time-dependent inhibition across strains at tested doses (1, 0.1, 0.01 g/L).	Initial high pH can inhibit growth, but many studies focus on adhesion/biodeterioration rather than dose-controlled viability in suspension.	Adds quantitative, dose-resolved data across strains under environmentally relevant loadings.	[86]
Biofilm formation (surface)	Lower on PC than on polystyrene; strain-specific effects: FA increased <i>S. aureus</i> biofilm formation; FA decreased <i>E. coli</i> and <i>P. aeruginosa</i> biofilm formation (up to 2 log ₁₀ CFU/cm ² vs. PC-REF).	Adhesion/biofilm formation depend on surface roughness, chemistry, and hydrophobicity; <i>P. aeruginosa</i> typically forms robust biofilms; decreasing pH/photocatalytic additives can reduce biofouling.	Extends the knowledge by quantifying strain-resolved biofilm shifts on FA-doped PC vs. PC-REF and a polymer reference material.	[88–91]
Algal ecotoxicity (<i>Desmodesmus subspicatus</i>)	<10 % growth inhibition at ≤1 g/L (low toxicity).	Concrete typically shows low algal toxicity; some non-cement materials show minimal to modest effects.	Comparable or lower toxicity than reported for concrete systems; aligns with environmentally benign profile.	[92,93]
Crustacean ecotoxicity (<i>Artemia salina</i>)	<10 % mortality at ≤1 g/L; no bioaccumulation observed.	<i>A. salina</i> is widely used for leachate toxicity; many environmental leachates cause substantial mortality depending on chemistry (NH ₄ ⁺ , metals, organics). Under chronic exposure, toxicity may increase and include growth-related endpoints such as reduced body length.	Our materials fall within non-toxic range vs. common leachates; supports low acute hazard. Our assays were short-term; this highlights the importance of chronic endpoints when benchmarking long-term risk.	[44,94, 95]
Plant phytotoxicity (<i>Sinapis alba</i>)	Slight phytotoxicity only at 1 g/L; negligible at lower doses.	High soil loading of PC dust (25 g/kg) caused direct germination inhibition in groundnut (<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>). Cement-paste leachates often show none or slight inhibition in <i>S. alba</i> and <i>L. sativum</i> tests.	Compared to <i>A. hypogaea</i> , our aqueous exposures ≤1 g/L showed only slight phytotoxicity at the highest dose; differences reflect matrix (soil vs. aqueous) and much higher dose. Comparable to benign outcomes reported for cementitious leachates (<i>S. alba</i> and <i>L. sativum</i>).	[38,96]
Scope	Single study spans scalable production, microstructure, bacteria (growth, biofilm, matrix interactions) and eukaryotic ecotoxicology.	Most studies address a single dimension: microstructure/leaching, microbial adhesion/biofilms, or isolated eukaryotic endpoints; cross-species panels within one study are rare.	Advance: end-to-end, cross-species benchmarking at environmentally relevant concentrations.	[38,44, 84–86, 88–93]

Future research should therefore include long-term leaching and aging experiments under realistic environmental conditions, as well as the use of more complex microbial consortia to better simulate real-world biofilm behaviour. Expanding the biological test battery to include higher-trophic organisms and chronic exposure scenarios would improve ecological relevance. Additionally, exploring varying FA sources and particle characteristics may clarify the influence of ash composition on both material performance and ecotoxicological outcomes. Such studies would provide a holistic understanding of the environmental safety and durability of FA-modified PC composites and their suitability for sustainable construction applications.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that FA-doped PC composites exhibit favourable structural properties and low biological toxicity, leading to the following conclusions:

- Detailed physicochemical analyses confirmed that FA consists primarily of quartz, mullite, magnetite, and rutile, with heterogeneous elemental distributions observed by EDS mapping. SEM and optical microscopy revealed predominantly spherical FA particles and a heterogeneous yet well-bonded microstructure in the composites.
- Incorporating FA into PC produced a denser, more homogeneous matrix with reduced portlandite and ettringite and enhanced C-S-H

formation, indicating active pozzolanic reactions and improved matrix densification.

- Biological assessments showed minimal effects on both prokaryotic and eukaryotic organisms at concentrations up to 1 g/L.
- Growth kinetics of *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa* were largely unaffected, with only a slight enhancement of *E. coli* growth rate. Biofilm formation was not promoted by FA nor PC materials and was strain-specific: *P. aeruginosa* formed more robust biofilms than *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, *E. coli* showed reduced biofilm formation on FA-doped composites, and *S. aureus* demonstrated enhanced adhesion on FA-containing surfaces compared to PC-REF.
- Ecotoxicological evaluations confirmed negligible effects of FA and PC on eukaryotic organisms. *D. subspicatus* growth inhibition was below 10 %, reflecting adaptation to transient alkaline conditions. *A. salina* mortality remained under 10 %, with no bioaccumulation observed, indicating low acute toxicity. Slight phytotoxicity on *S. alba* occurred only at the highest concentration (1 g/L), likely caused by calcium hydroxide-related alkalinity.
- Overall, incorporating FA into PC improved microstructure and durability while maintaining a low ecotoxicological risk.

These findings highlight the importance of assessing both material properties and biological responses to ensure environmentally safer, sustainable construction materials, as species- and strain-specific behaviour in materials presence is a common phenomenon. Regarding overall environmental impact, since the blended binder based on PC and

FA is environmentally and health-safe, it represents a sustainable alternative to ordinary PC. The approach also promotes the reuse of an energetic by-product, thereby supporting circular economy principles. The use of such eco-efficient blended binders brings multiple advantages, including reduced production costs, lower CO₂ emissions, and decreased energy consumption during binder manufacture. In addition, the partial substitution of PC by FA contributes to improved thermal and volumetric stability of the material. Due to the slower hydration kinetics and reduced heat evolution characteristic of pozzolanic materials, these binders are particularly suitable for the construction of large-volume structural elements, where they help minimize the risk of autogenous shrinkage and thermal cracking. Consequently, they enable the production of massive concrete structures without the need for special cooling or curing procedures, while maintaining long-term durability and performance.

Supporting Information

Chemical composition of PC used (Table S1), XRD pattern of PC (Figure S1), chemical composition of the prepared samples (PC-REF, PC-FA10, PC-FA20) determined by XRF (Figure S2).

AI statements

During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI tools, Grammarly and ChatGPT, to correct grammar and improve text readability. All AI-generated suggestions were reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Simona Lencova: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Jana Kofronova:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Vaclav Peroutka:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Zbysek Pavlik:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Milena Pavlikova:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Adela Kubistova:** Investigation, Data curation. **Oskar Chmel:** Investigation, Data curation. **Michal Lojka:** Investigation, Data curation. **Adela Jirickova:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Ondrej Jankovsky:** Supervision, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.rineng.2025.108364.

Data availability

According to open science principles, data can be found at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16985242.

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